

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth system**

Initialisation and verification of NEMO configuration

Deliverable D5.7

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Cover sheet: A figure illustrating NEMO-simulated ventilation of the bottom Southern Ocean- Author: Casimir de Lavergne (CNRS)**Disclaimer:** Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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History of Changes

Version	Date	Comment	Authors
Version 1	8 April 2025	Submitted version	Casimir de Lavergne
Version 2	3 March 2026	Re-numbering of the sections	Chiara Bearzotti

1. Publishable summary

This deliverable describes a numerical simulation of the global ocean state. This simulation has been run for over 1500 model years, so that ocean currents and seawater properties have reached a quasi-steady state. This equilibrated model ocean state is meant to be as close as possible to the real ocean state in the 1990s. We show that key features of this model ocean are indeed in good agreement with observations. We also present a methodology to subject this model ocean to perturbations in Antarctic freshwater fluxes. Finally, we introduce purposeful tracers in the model to analyse the spreading and impacts on ocean ventilation of anomalous freshwater fluxes from the Antarctic ice sheet.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of the work performed

2.1.1 Set-up, spin-up and evaluation of global ocean model configuration

We have used a configuration of the Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean (NEMO) ocean model that has a nominal horizontal resolution of one degree and 75 layers. This configuration is documented in an article submitted to the *Journal of Advances in Modelling Earth Systems*. The article acknowledges OCEAN ICE and is already available as a pre-print in open access:

de Lavergne, Rathore, Madec, Sallée, Ethé, Nasser, Millet and Vancoppenolle. Effects of improved tidal mixing in NEMO one-degree global ocean model. *ESS Open Archive* (2024). <https://doi.org/10.22541/essoar.173152139.95978362/v1>

The ingredients of this configuration are also publicly available on Zenodo:

de Lavergne, Rathore, Madec, Sallée, Ethé, Nasser, Millet and Vancoppenolle. NEMO4.2 eORCA1 configuration files for stable millennial ocean simulations. Zenodo (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14041098>

The simulation most relevant to OCEAN ICE, called 'TRA' in the submitted article, has been run for 1500 years under a prescribed atmosphere following the COREv2 normal year forcing (Large and Yeager 2009). It includes the most comprehensive representation of tidal vertical mixing. In the article we have shown that the simulated stratification and circulation are quasi steady by model year 1000; only a slight temperature drift continues through model year 1500. Furthermore, the simulated density stratification is in excellent agreement with observations (Figure 1). Remarkably, the production of Antarctic Bottom Water in this simulation occurs in the correct locations, at four shelf sites that correspond to the observed sites (cf Figure 14 of the pre-print). The global overturning circulation is also realistic with an upper cell transporting 18 Sv at 26°N in the Atlantic and a lower cell transporting up to 16 Sv at 64°S (10 Sv at 30°S) (Figure 2). This realism gives confidence in the configuration's suitability to investigate the response of Antarctic Bottom Water to Antarctic meltwater perturbations.

The year 1500 of experiment TRA will serve as our initial state for perturbation experiments.

Fig. 1: Basin-averaged density (**a,d,g**), temperature (**b,e,h**) and salinity (**c,f,i**) profiles in the observational climatology of Gouretski (2019) (red) and in model experiments OLD (black), NEW (light blue) and TRA (dark blue). The Pacific Ocean (33°S-65°N) is shown in panels (**a-c**), the Atlantic Ocean (33°S-65°N) in panels (**d-f**) and the Southern Ocean (80°S-33°S) in panels (**g-i**). Density is measured as σ_2 , the potential density referenced to 2000 dbars. Model output is averaged over years 991-1000.

Fig. 2: Meridional overturning streamfunction in experiment TRA averaged over model years 1491-1500. The streamfunction is shown for the Indian-Pacific (a,b), Atlantic (c,d) and global (e,f) oceans. It was computed both in depth coordinate (a,c,e) and density (σ_2) coordinate (b,d,f). The density-coordinate streamfunction is reprojected to depth using the pseudo-depth of isopycnal surfaces. The pseudo-depth of an isopycnal surface within a given latitude band is the geopotential which has the same volume beneath it. The shown streamfunctions include both resolved and parameterized components of advection.

2.1.2 Passive tracers to track ocean ventilation and meltwater perturbations

To study the response of ocean ventilation, and in particular the evolution of major water masses such as North Atlantic Deep Water and Antarctic Bottom Water, the model simulation includes six regional dye tracers plus an ‘ideal age’ tracer. Regional dye tracers are restored to 1 at the surface over a given regional patch, and to 0 elsewhere at the surface. The ‘ideal age’ tracer is restored to 0 at the surface globally and increases at a rate of one second per second in the ocean interior. These seven tracers provide a

comprehensive picture of the simulated global ocean ventilation. They are fully equilibrated in our reference simulation, thanks to a two-step procedure. First, they were spun up *offline* (that is, with ocean velocity, diffusivity and stratification fields read from a file rather than computed) for 6000 years. Second, they were injected into the *online* simulation at model year 1000 and evolved until model year 1500 to perfect the equilibration.

The distributions of the dye tracers and ideal age are documented in an article submitted to the *Journal of Advances in Modelling Earth Systems* and available as a pre-print in open access:

Millet, de Lavergne, Gray, Ethé, Madec, Holzer, DeVries, Gebbie, Roche. Global ocean ventilation: a comparison between a general circulation model and data-constrained inverse models. *ESS Open Archive* (2024). <https://doi.org/10.22541/essoar.173532470.03609119/v1>

Figure 3 below shows the fraction of the global ocean volume occupied by each dye, in the *online* simulation from model year 1000 to 1500. The time series illustrates the near steadiness of the dye tracer distributions. At year 1500 of the simulation, 37% of the global ocean is ventilated from the North Atlantic (NA), 37% from the Antarctic margins (AA) and 16% from high southern latitudes (HS). Under increased Antarctic meltwater fluxes, we expect ventilation to slow and especially a contraction of the volume ventilated from Antarctic margins. This ventilation change will be diagnosed and quantified using our dye tracers.

Fig. 3: Percentage of the global ocean volume filled by each dye, as a function of model year, in the online simulation called 'TRA'. Year 1500 serves as our initial state for perturbation experiments. AA corresponds to Antarctic margins (80°S-65°S), HS to high southern latitudes (45°S-65°S), MS to mid southern latitudes (45°S-30°S), LL to low latitudes (30°S-30°N), NP to the northern North Pacific (30°N-67°N) and NA to the northern (>30°N) North Atlantic and Arctic.

To identify the pathways of the meltwater perturbations, passive anomaly tracers of temperature (PAT) and salinity (PAS) have been coded and will be included in our perturbation experiments. The concept of PAS and

PAT was pioneered by Silvy et al. (2022). PAS and PAT are conservative tracers propagating according to the modelled advection and diffusion, with a source term that represents the anomaly of salinity (or temperature) induced by the imposed perturbation in air-sea or ice-sea fluxes. In our case, we want PAS and PAT tracers that track the anomalies induced by modified Antarctic meltwater fluxes. We coded six passive tracers, one PAS and PAT for each of three types of meltwater perturbation: iceberg melt, Antarctic surface runoff and sub-shelf melt (Coulon et al. 2024). These six passive tracers will enable to separate the impacts of each type of freshwater perturbation, but also to disentangle the passive response of ocean temperature and salinity fields from their active response (i.e. the response resulting from a change in dynamics that reorganizes water masses).

Fig. 4: Validation of PAS and PAT tracers in an idealized ‘antwater’ experiment (Swart et al. 2023). a) Anomaly of sea surface salinity (a) and sea surface temperature (c) in the ‘antwater’ perturbation experiment at month 12 of the simulation. Sea surface distribution of PAS (b) and PAT (d) tracers at month 12 of the same simulation.

To validate PAS and PAT tracers and benchmark our model, we performed an idealized ‘antwater’ experiment, following the SOFIA framework (Swart et al. 2023). In this experiment, 0.1 Sv of 0°C freshwater

is released uniformly over coastal grid cells around Antarctica, at the surface. Figure 4 shows the simulated anomalies (perturbation experiment – control experiment) of sea surface salinity and sea surface temperature after 12 months of simulation. The perturbation experiment displays the expected strong surface freshening around Antarctica (Figure 4a), which is primarily a passive response to the imposed freshwater addition, as evidenced by the analogous surface pattern of the PAS tracer (Figure 4b). The temperature response is more complex and not merely passive (Figure 4c,d): the release of 0°C water tends to warm the initially near-freezing coastal waters (Figure 4d), but surface temperature changes are also driven by changes in salinity stratification and sea ice (not shown), leading to amplified coastal surface warming and surface cooling further offshore (Figure 4c). Overall, this analysis shows the soundness and value of our PAS and PAT tracers.

2.1.3 Prescribing fluxes associated with salinity restoring and freshwater budget control

To perform hosing experiments in an ocean model which is not coupled to an atmospheric model, it is desirable to modify the computation of two freshwater fluxes that may otherwise confound the response.

The first such flux is associated with restoring of sea surface salinity toward observations. This restoring is necessary to compensate for missing atmospheric feedbacks and biases in the forcing fields. In our freshwater perturbation experiments, restoring toward observed sea surface salinity would remove a sizeable fraction of the freshwater added, typically 30 to 50% (e.g., Lago and England 2019, Swart et al. 2023). It would also prevent controlling precisely the imposed freshwater perturbation.

The second flux is due to the need to close the freshwater budget in ocean-only simulations. In our TRA experiment, freshwater budget closure is ensured at each time step by calculating the global volume imbalance of the ocean-sea ice system and adding a globally uniform freshwater flux that corrects for this imbalance (see de Lavergne et al. 2024). This is a standard method, but it is problematic for a hosing experiment, since it will compensate for any localized freshwater addition by a globally uniform freshwater extraction (i.e. an increase in evaporation).

To avoid these issues, we followed recommendations from Swart et al. (2023). In detail, we ran our ‘supercontrol’ simulation (aka experiment ‘TRA’) for 500 extra years (model years 1501 to 2000) with the two above-mentioned fluxes saved at a frequency of 6 hours. Then, we ran a new ‘control’ simulation where these two fluxes are not computed interactively but instead prescribed from the 6-hourly output of the ‘supercontrol’ simulation. From this new ‘control’ experiment, freshwater perturbations can be imposed without being counteracted by salinity restoring and freshwater budget terms. This procedure is a crucial methodological step and an improvement over many past studies using ocean-only models (e.g., Li et al. 2023).

Figure 5 shows the evolution of three key ocean circulation metrics over model years 1500-1750 in both ‘supercontrol’ and ‘control’ experiments. The ‘supercontrol’ simulation is almost steady. The ‘control’ experiment is quasi steady during the first 30 years of simulation; until about year 125 of the simulation, it shows small but acceptable drift; beyond 125 years, the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation starts to decline and the circulation becomes unrealistic. Prescribed restoring and freshwater budget fluxes thus allow for a stable simulation only over a centennial timescale. This is consistent with previous studies employing the same strategy: these studies found similar levels of drift and restricted their analysis to less than 100 years (e.g., Boeira Dias et al. 2021).

2.1.4 Strategies to reduce drift in the control experiment and explore longer timescales

We planned to run perturbed simulations over multiple centuries, up to calendar year 3000. This is not possible with the current method, which prescribes freshwater fluxes associated with salinity restoring and freshwater budget control. With this method, the ocean state in our control simulation is stable for only about 125 years (Figure 5). We are currently exploring alternative methods to be able to study the response of the ocean over multiple centuries. Alternatives being explored are:

- Keep interactive restoring and freshwater budget terms, but factor in their contribution to net freshwater perturbations;
- Keep interactive restoring, but restore towards observed sea surface salinity + surface PAS, so that the restoring is aware of the imposed freshwater perturbation and does not overreact;
- Add a restoring towards surface salinity of the ‘supercontrol’ simulation, then prescribe this additional restoring flux.

Fig. 5: Time series of Antarctic Circumpolar Current strength at Drake Passage **(a)**, Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation strength at 26°N **(b)** and Antarctic Bottom Water transport at 64°S (dashed) and 30°S (solid) **(c)**. Black corresponds to the ‘supercontrol’ simulation (referred to as ‘TRA’), which is very stable. Blue is the ‘control’ simulation with prescribed (instead of interactive) freshwater fluxes associated with surface salinity restoring and freshwater budget closure, which is only stable over about 125 years.

2.2 References

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2.3 Open Science

The NEMO code is publicly available at: <https://forge.nemo-ocean.eu/nemo/nemo/-/releases> The version employed in this work is version 4.2.0.

The configuration files used have been deposited on Zenodo in open access: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14041098>

The steady-state age and dye tracer distributions documented in Millet et al. (2024) have been deposited as an open-access dataset on SEANOE: <https://doi.org/10.17882/103915>

Two articles linked to this work have been submitted to the *Journal of Advances in Modelling Earth Systems*. They are available as open-access pre-prints:

- de Lavergne, Rathore, Madec, Sallée, Ethé, Nasser, Millet and Vancoppenolle. Effects of improved tidal mixing in NEMO one-degree global ocean model. *ESS Open Archive* (2024). <https://doi.org/10.22541/essoar.173152139.95978362/v1>
- Millet, de Lavergne, Gray, Ethé, Madec, Holzer, DeVries, Gebbie, Roche. Global ocean ventilation: a comparison between a general circulation model and data-constrained inverse models. *ESS Open Archive* (2024). <https://doi.org/10.22541/essoar.173532470.03609119/v1>

A poster on this work is going to be presented at the EGU General Assembly 2025

<https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU25/EGU25-11251.html>

3. Results

This work advances understanding of the ocean's response to changes in the Antarctic ice sheet and will inform policies through reports such as the IPCC AR7.

The present work also involves developing and evaluating the NEMO modelling platform, which is used for operational oceanography, weather predictions, climate projections, and ocean and climate research.

4. Impact

This deliverable contributes to achieving the project's objectives, as described in the action description.

O5: Assess how global ocean circulation is impacted by freshwater discharge from the northern and southern ice sheets.

This deliverable contributes to this specific objective by documenting the baseline ocean state simulated with NEMO and the modelling choices made. It sets the stage for investigating the response of key ocean circulation features and ventilation pathways to freshwater discharge.

O7: Deliver free and open access to all data obtained in the project and contribute to international assessments (e.g. IPCC), climate model development, multi-national ocean observing initiatives (e.g. SOOS, All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance) and policymakers.

This deliverable contributes to this specific objective by providing open-access model configuration files that will serve the ocean and climate modelling communities. For example, the ocean model configuration documented here guides the ongoing development of the IPSLCM7 climate model. Ultimately, the work described in this deliverable will serve IPCC assessment reports.